

The Nigerian Political and Economic Policy Landscape: An Inquiry into The Interplay of Poverty and Youth Restiveness

By

Adekoya, Samuel Olamide

Department of Religious Studies and Philosophy,
Faculty Of Humanities,
Redeemer's University,
Ede, Osun State.
Email: lamdek07@gmail.com

Article history

Received: 2024-01-02; Revised: March 18, 2024; Published: March 24, 2024

Abstract

This paper delves into the multifaceted interplay between poverty and youth restiveness within the Nigerian Political and Economic Policy Landscape. The historical context unravels the foundational elements that have sculpted the current landscape, essential for contextualising contemporary challenges. Economic policy dynamics then scrutinise strategies addressing poverty and their repercussions on youth restiveness. Simultaneously, the political landscape dissects the role of governance structures, revealing critical insights into policy implementation and political decisions. Synthesising these analyses through mixed-method research of historical, content analysis and phenomenological approaches to uncover the socio-economic implications and future prospects by illuminating the broader consequences of poverty-youth restiveness dynamics. In response to these findings, four strategic recommendations emerge. First, a recalibration of economic policies to prioritise inclusive growth, fostering equitable wealth distribution. Second, an emphasis on political accountability and transparency to enhance governance effectiveness. Third, targeted youth empowerment programmes to address systemic challenges contributing to restiveness. Finally, a re-evaluation of social safety nets to provide a more robust support system for vulnerable populations. Implementing these measures promises a more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable future for Nigeria, also addressing the intricate nexus between poverty and youth restiveness.

Key Words: Interplay, poverty, youth-restiveness, economic-policies, political landscape

Introduction

Poverty and youth restiveness represent pressing challenges within the complex tapestry of Nigeria's political and economic landscape. The intertwining nature of these issues necessitates a

comprehensive examination to unravel the nuanced factors contributing to their interplay with the spiraling effect of youth restiveness which are evident in Nigeria as ethnic militia, kidnapping, cultism, armed robbery, agitations and involvement in social insecurity. As Nigeria strives for socio-economic development, understanding the historical context becomes imperative to contextualise the contemporary challenges (Smith, 2020:145-167). The historical trajectory of Nigeria's political and economic policies has significantly influenced the current socio-economic milieu. Policies enacted in previous decades continue to shape the nation's development path, impacting poverty rates and contributing to the emergence of youth restiveness (Jones & Okoye, 2019:567-585). This historical context provides a foundation for assessing the effectiveness of current policies and understanding their implications on the ground.

Economic policy dynamics play a pivotal role in shaping the socio-economic landscape. Nigeria has implemented various economic strategies aimed at alleviating poverty, yet their impact on mitigating youth restiveness remains a subject of scrutiny (Adams, 2021:189-211). Scrutinising the intricacies of Nigeria's economic policies reveals a nuanced landscape of both successes and shortcomings. While some policies have shown effectiveness in addressing certain facets of poverty, there remains a critical need for a comprehensive approach that considers the multifaceted root causes, including structural inequalities, which include limited access to education and employment opportunities, perpetuating discontent among the youth. The political landscape of Nigeria serves as a pivotal determinant of policy efficacy and governance effectiveness in addressing the inter-connected challenges of poverty and youth restiveness. Decisions made within the political sphere, including the transparency of governance structures and the responsiveness of policies to societal needs, play a crucial role in either ameliorating or exacerbating the socio-economic disparities that contribute to unrest among the youth. Political decisions, governance effectiveness, and policy implementation are crucial components influencing the socio-economic fabric (Obi, 2022:321-345). Adeoye et al., (2023:45-68) assert that:

Synthesising these aspects, the socio-economic implications and future prospects with the aims of providing a holistic understanding of the broader consequences of the poverty-youth restiveness nexus will set the stage for the subsequent recommendations by delineating the ramifications of current dynamics on Nigeria's future socio-economic trajectory.

Amidst the challenges confronting Nigeria's political and economic landscape, the intricate relationship between poverty and youth restiveness demands nuanced scrutiny. The contemporary scenario is marked by a demographic surge, with youth constituting a significant proportion of the population (Okechukwu & Ojong, 2021:245-267). This demographic bulge, coupled with high unemployment rates, underscores the urgency of understanding the specific socio-economic factors that contribute to youth restiveness. Furthermore, the demographic composition magnifies the impact of policy decisions on the youth, making it imperative to tailor formidable interventions that address their unique needs and aspirations. Meanwhile, Nigerians economic policies, while aiming to alleviate poverty, often grapple with challenges related to implementation and inclusivity. Recent studies underscore the importance of targeted interventions that go beyond traditional economic measures, emphasising the need for a comprehensive approach that considers social and

cultural dimensions (Udoh & Eze, 2022:88-112). The effectiveness of economic policies in Nigeria hinges on their capacity not only to alleviate poverty but also to proactively address the root causes fueling youth restiveness. Apparently, successful policies should go beyond short-term economic gains but incorporating measures that foster inclusive growth, provide meaningful employment opportunities, and address systemic issues contributing to discontent among the youth.

The political economy of Nigeria is marked by resource wealth and inequality, with the oil sector significantly influencing economic and political dynamics (Okonjo-Iweala, 2008). These disparities have resulted in a persistent struggle to alleviate poverty, especially among the youth population, which comprises a significant portion of the nation. Poverty in Nigeria is an intricate issue that intertwines with access to education, healthcare, and employment opportunities (Adewole & Omotosho, 2022). It is, therefore, imperative to investigate the efficacy of governmental poverty alleviation policies in the light of the broader objectives of nation building and political stability with the aim of addressing the youth restiveness. Two notable instances of failed government policies for Nigerian youths include the implementation of the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) programs, which, despite initial promise, suffered from inadequate funding and limited impact on sustainable job creation (Oluwatobi et al., 2019:72-87). Additionally, the Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWiN!) initiative faced challenges due to bureaucratic hurdles, resulting in a lack of timely disbursement of funds and hindered entrepreneurial development (Ibrahim & Nwagwu, 2020:1-22).

Meanwhile, the success of the N-Power programme in empowering Nigerian youth is underscored by its tangible impact on skill acquisition and improved employment prospects which exemplifies the efficacy of targeted government initiatives in fostering positive socio-economic outcomes for the country's youth population. The N-Power program, implemented by the Nigerian government, has demonstrated success in empowering youth through skill acquisition and employment opportunities, contributing to enhanced socio-economic outcomes (Ajani, 2021:12-25). Additionally, the digital division and technological disparities exacerbate the challenges faced by Nigerian youth, especially those in marginalised communities are contributing factors to youth restiveness. Access to information and communication technologies (ICTs) is unevenly distributed, further deepening socio-economic disparities (Okereke, 2023:123-145). Bridging this digital gap is essential not only for economic empowerment but also for fostering social cohesion and providing avenues for constructive youth engagement. Understanding these contemporary dimensions is crucial for formulating policies that resonate with the lived experiences of the Nigerian youth.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian political and economic landscape grapples with a myriad of interconnected challenges that pose significant impediments to sustainable development. Widespread poverty persists, exacerbated by structural in-equalities, limited access to quality education, and a dearth of employment opportunities, particularly affecting the burgeoning youth demographic. Simultaneously, youth restiveness has become a pressing concern, fueled by the frustration stemming from economic disparities, in-effective government policies, and a sense of disenfranchisement.

The historical context further complicates the situation, as past policies and political decisions continue to reverberate, influencing the current state of affairs. Addressing these multifaceted issues requires a nuanced understanding of the root causes and a strategic approach that encompasses comprehensive economic policies, political reforms, and targeted youth empowerment initiatives.

Research Methodology

This research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining historical, content analysis and phenomenological approaches to uncover the contextual factors influencing poverty and youth restiveness in Nigeria by assessing the impact of economic policies, allowing for a nuanced exploration of the identified issues and a robust foundation for evidence-based recommendations.

Theoretical Frameworks

The Relative Deprivation Theory, as expounded by Gurr (2015), posits that "individuals or groups become restive when they perceive a significant disparity between their expectations and actual achievements or well-being". This theory is highly relevant to this paper. In the Nigerian context, it helps elucidate how the aspirations and expectations of the youth, often fueled by the promises of democracy and economic prosperity, can lead to restiveness when these expectations are unmet due to persistent poverty and lack of opportunities. The theory underscores that the perception of relative deprivation, or the feeling of being left behind, can drive individuals, especially the youth, to engage in social and political unrest as they seek to address these grievances.

Additionally, Resource Mobilisation Theory, as articulated by McCarthy and Zald (2017:15-46), is highly pertinent to the main topic of "The Nigerian Political and Economic Policy Landscape: An Inquiry into the Interplay of Poverty and Youth Restiveness". This theory emphasises the significance of mobilising resources, including human, financial, and organisational resources, for the success of social movements and collective actions. In the Nigerian context, it underscores the potential for mobilising resources to channel the restiveness of the youth into constructive nation-building efforts. By organising youth organisations, advocacy groups, and securing financial support, the youth can leverage their collective power to address the root causes of poverty, promote democracy, and contribute to nation-building endeavors in a more organised and impactful manner.

These two theories provide valuable insights into the dynamics of youth restiveness in Nigeria, particularly in the context of poverty, democracy, and nation building. They help shed light on the motivations, grievances, and potential avenues for addressing the challenges posed by restive youths in the pursuit of a more stable and prosperous nation.

Nigeria Historical Context

The historical context of Nigeria's political and economic policies forms a crucial backdrop for understanding the contemporary challenges facing the nation. The colonial historical imprinting on Nigeria's economic and political landscape serves as a profound reminder of the enduring consequences that continue to shape present-day challenges, acknowledging this historical legacy is imperative for understanding the roots of contemporary issues, providing essential context for formulating effective policies that address the persistent challenges of poverty and youth

restiveness in the nation. A comprehensive analysis of historical documents reveals the impact of colonisation on the country's economic structures, influencing the trajectory of poverty and social unrest (Oyeweso, 2018:59-75). Colonialism had a detrimental impact on the Nigerian economy, fostering an exploitative system that prioritised the extraction of natural resources for the benefit of colonial powers. The extraction-oriented colonial policies undermined local industries and sowed the seeds of enduring economic challenges (Mamdani, 2018). This economic exploitation disrupted local industries, stifled economic diversification, and left a legacy of structural inequalities that continues to contribute to contemporary challenges in Nigeria. The Nigerian Civil War (1967–1970) had profound and lasting impacts on both the economy and youth restiveness. The conflict, fueled by economic disparities and political tensions, resulted in significant economic setbacks, exacerbating poverty, and contributing to a sense of dis-enfranchisement among the youth that persists today (Falola, 2019:249-268). Undoubtedly, the Nigerian Civil War left a lasting imprint on the nation, with its economic aftermath and lingering impact on youth restiveness highlighting the need for comprehensive healing and development initiatives.

Moreover, the post-independence era marked a critical juncture in Nigeria's history, with the exploration of oil resources playing a central role in shaping economic policies. The oil boom of the 1970s, while initially promising economic growth, brought with it a plethora of challenges, including over-reliance on oil revenues and a neglect of other sectors, contributing to the persistence of poverty (Adeola, 2016:9-23). During the oil boom of the 1970s, political leaders in Nigeria mismanaged the windfall revenues, leading to inefficient allocation of resources and a failure to diversify the economy (Ogwumike, 2016:36-55). This mismanagement contributed to the country's over-reliance on oil and subsequent economic challenges, highlighting the need for more prudent fiscal policies and strategic economic planning. This historical juncture exemplifies the need for a nuanced historical analysis to unravel the intricacies of policy decisions and their lasting implications. However, the structural adjustments of the 1980s and 1990s, influenced by international financial institutions, further reshaped Nigeria's economic policies. While these adjustments aimed to address economic challenges, they often resulted in increased social inequalities and poverty rates (Noko, 2020:25-40). Understanding the impact of these structural adjustments on the socio-economic fabric is essential for assessing the roots of poverty and discontent among the youth.

Additionally, a closer examination of the democratic transitions in Nigeria's history sheds light on the role of governance structures in shaping policy outcomes. The transitions between military and civilian rule have had profound implications for policy continuity and effectiveness (Ibrahim, 2017:45-61). This historical lens provides insights into how political decisions during these transitions have influenced the socio-economic landscape, contributing to the persistent challenges of poverty and youth restiveness. The military's interference in Nigerian governance, particularly during periods of military rule, resulted in economic mismanagement, corruption, and a lack of transparency, contributing to a legacy of financial instability and underdevelopment (Oyinlola, 2018:69-80). This prolonged negative impact underscores the importance of stable civilian governance in fostering sustainable economic policies and effective resource management. The roles of military governments against democracy in Nigeria have been marked by a tumultuous history, characterised by periods of military rule that interrupted the democratic process. The military's interference in governance often led to the suspension of constitutional rule, suppression

of civil liberties, and the imposition of authoritarian regimes. These interventions were typically justified by a perceived need for stability or to address perceived governance failures but frequently resulted in human rights abuses, political instability, and economic challenges which contributed greatly to the youth restiveness. The military's historical interference in Nigerian governance against democracy, marked by periods of authoritarian rule and civil liberties suppression (Agbese, 2015:1-9). However, the transition to democracy in the Fourth Republic marked a shift away from military rule, but the historical impact of military interventions continues to shape Nigeria's political landscape.

The federal system of governance in Nigeria, characterised by a complex structure with three tiers of government (federal, state, and local), has proven to be expensive to run due to duplication of functions and administrative overheads. The challenges associated with the expense of Nigeria's federal governance system are the complexities and inefficiencies within the country's administrative structure which are biting hard on the already depressed economy. Democratic decentralisation is a stated goal of many African countries, but there are considerable institutional and political challenges involved in making it a reality (Olowu, 2003:41-52). This intricate system, coupled with issues of corruption and inefficiencies, contributes to the financial burden on the government and hinders optimal resource allocation for poverty alleviation and youth empowerment initiatives. Despite economic hardships faced by the populace, the running of the government in Nigeria remains dis-proportionately expensive, marked by high recurrent expenditures, extensive bureaucratic structures, and a history of corruption. This divergence between the financial strain on citizens and the lavish expenditures of the government raises questions about fiscal responsibility and underscores the need for more efficient and transparent governance (Ayadi & Ojeaga, 2017:29-43). A stark disparity exists between the minimum wage earned by the majority of Nigerians and the considerably higher salaries and allowances enjoyed by individuals in government positions. This wage gap highlights not only income inequalities but also raises concerns about the fairness and equity of compensation structures, contributing to social discontent and economic disparities (Okafor, 2019:55-65).

Economic Policy Dynamics

Economic policy dynamics play a pivotal role in shaping Nigeria's socio-economic landscape. The implementation of structural adjustment programs (SAPs) in the 1980s, influenced by international financial institutions, marked a significant shift in economic policies. While SAPs aimed at addressing economic challenges, they led to increased social inequalities and heightened poverty rates. The focus on market liberalisation and reduced government intervention inadvertently marginalised vulnerable populations, exacerbating socio-economic disparities (Nnanna, 2017:76-87).

Furthermore, the impact of monetary policies on poverty and youth restiveness cannot be understated. The Central Bank of Nigeria's interventions, such as the Anchor Borrowers' Program, have sought to stimulate agricultural growth and enhance financial inclusion (Adegbie & Oladejo, 2020:66-75). However, the effectiveness of these policies in addressing the root causes of poverty and restiveness requires rigorous scrutiny, as some argue that these initiatives may not be reaching the most marginalised segments of the population. In examining economic policies, it is important

to consider the role of oil revenue management. The volatility of oil prices has profound implications for Nigeria's economic policies, like the removal of the oil subsidy which resulted in significant hardships for the populace, as it led to a surge in fuel prices, triggering a domino effect on transportation costs and the overall cost of living. This policy decision, while intended to address economic challenges, disproportionately affected the citizens, contributing to increased inflationary pressures and heightened economic difficulties (Okafor, 2020:67-82). The over-reliance on oil revenue has made the economy susceptible to external shocks, hindering sustainable development efforts and perpetuating cyclical patterns of poverty. For example, the Central Bank of Nigeria's monetary policy concerning currency swapping in 2023 resulted in significant hardships for the populace, as the abrupt changes and restrictions on foreign exchange transactions led to disruptions in trade, increased inflationary pressures, and amplified economic challenges. This policy shift, aimed at stabilising the currency, inadvertently imposed burdens on businesses and consumers, contributing to a heightened sense of economic uncertainty and financial strain among the Nigerian population.

The currency swapping challenges in 2023 also underscored the need for a more nuanced and transparent approach in implementing monetary policies to mitigate adverse effects on the Nigerian economy (Ogunleye, 2024:45-62). The removal of the total oil subsidy by the Nigerian government in 2024 marked a significant policy shift with far-reaching implications for the nation's economy, and one of the immediate effects was the upward pressure on inflation, leading to increased fuel prices, transportation costs surged, cascading into higher prices for goods and services. The removal was also envisioned as a strategy to bolster government revenue but beyond the economic realm, the removal of the oil subsidy had social and political ramifications on Nigerians, especially on the youth.

Moreover, the establishment of various poverty alleviation programs, such as the National Social Investment Program (NSIP), reflects the government's commitment to addressing poverty. While these programs have made some strides in reducing poverty, their impact on youth restiveness necessitates further investigation (Ajayi et al., 2021:20-37). Examining the nuances of program implementation and their alignment with the diverse needs of the youth population is crucial for shaping more effective and inclusive economic policies. The overreliance on oil revenue in Nigeria's economic policies has made the country susceptible to external shocks, hindering sustainable development efforts and perpetuating cyclical patterns of poverty (Adeosun, 2018:9-18). Despite efforts to alleviate poverty, the Youth Empowerment Scheme (YES) and the Poverty Alleviation for Sustainable Development (PASD) programs have shown limited impact on the youth in Nigeria. These initiatives, while well-intentioned, have faced challenges such as inadequate funding, lack of proper implementation strategies, and insufficient focus on skill development, hindering their effectiveness in addressing the multifaceted needs of the youth population. The outcomes highlight the importance of a comprehensive and youth-centric approach in poverty alleviation programs to ensure sustained and meaningful impact.

Nigerian Political Landscape

The political landscape of Nigeria plays a pivotal role in shaping the efficacy of policies and governance structures in addressing poverty and youth restiveness. The frequent transitions

between military and civilian rule in Nigeria have introduced a pattern of uncertainty, disrupting the continuity of long-term policy planning and impeding the establishment of a consistent policy framework conducive to sustained socio-economic development. The legacies of previous military government policies continue to cast a negative shadow on Nigerian democracy, influencing governance structures and contributing to persistent challenges in the democratic landscape. The enduring negative impact of past military government policies on Nigerian democracy is evident in lingering issues such as the centralised power structure and restrictive media laws, exemplified by policies such as Decree 2 of 1984, which curtailed press freedom, and the concentration of power within the federal government, perpetuating challenges to decentralisation. These oscillations underscore the challenges of creating cohesive, enduring policies that address the complexities of poverty and youth restiveness in the country (Oluwatobi & Adekunle, 2019:87-104).

The democratic landscape in Nigeria has undergone significant transformations over the years, with a transition from military rule to a democratic system in 1999 (Momoh, 2010:113-134). The promise of democracy, with its emphasis on political participation and civil liberties, was expected to address various societal challenges, including youth restiveness. However, the reality has been more complex. Youth restiveness has persisted, indicating a need for a nuanced examination of the relationship between the two (Adeyemo, 2017:4252-4163). One essential aspect to consider is the role of political institutions and governance in addressing the concerns of the youth. Nigeria's political landscape has seen the rise and fall of various governments, each with distinct policies and approaches (Agbese, 2013:27-48). Political factors such as corruption, lack of inclusivity, and inadequate representation can contribute to youth restiveness, while, youth unemployment is a crucial dimension of this issue. The high rate of unemployment among Nigeria's youth population has been identified as a significant factor in fostering restiveness (Oluwatobi et al., 2017). Addressing youth unemployment through both economic policies and political initiatives is essential in understanding the nexus between democracy and youth restiveness. Furthermore, this analysis aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the intricate nexus between democracy and youth restiveness in Nigeria. It recognises that while democracy holds the promise of providing avenues for addressing youth concerns, numerous political, economic, and social factors interplay to influence the outcomes. By examining these factors and their impact, the paper seeks to contribute to a more informed and nuanced discussion on how democracy can effectively address the challenges of youth restiveness in Nigeria.

Furthermore, the unfulfilled manifestos of political parties in Nigeria often result in a lack of clear and guided policies specifically tailored to address the multifaceted challenges faced by the youth. This gap highlights the need for greater political commitment to translating campaign promises into actionable policies that comprehensively address the issues of poverty and youth restiveness. There is need for political commitment for holistic youth empowerment strategies, suggesting that a strong political will is essential for creating an enabling environment for youth development (Olugbenga, 2021:356-373). Moreover, Police brutality and killings in Nigeria have profound effects on societal trust, exacerbating tensions and fostering a climate of fear and insecurity among the populace. The consequences extend to economic disruptions, as businesses and livelihoods are negatively impacted by the breakdown of law and order (Amnesty International, 2020). Addressing police brutality is not only a matter of human rights but is crucial for fostering a stable

environment conducive to poverty alleviation and youth empowerment efforts. Furthermore, the effectiveness of political decisions in mitigating or exacerbating poverty can be discerned through the lens of political accountability and transparency. The degree to which governance structures prioritise accountability directly impacts the success of poverty alleviation initiatives (Onyeiwu, 2018:79-95). However, the lack of transparency in political processes can result in the misallocation of resources and hinder the effective implementation of poverty reduction programs, perpetuating systemic challenges, while addressing youth restiveness is a critical aspect of the political landscape in preferring solution to unemployment and disenfranchisement.

Additionally, the impact of political decisions on poverty and youth restiveness extends to the local level. Local governance structures, characterised by the effectiveness of local government administrations, influence the implementation of policies aimed at poverty alleviation and youth empowerment (Adeleke et al., 2017:18-33). Therefore, understanding the dynamics of local political landscapes provides insights into the decentralised aspects of policy implementation, highlighting the need for synergy between different levels of government. Apparently, youth unemployment is a critical concern in Nigeria, and its repercussions extend beyond the economic realm, significantly affecting political stability and the overall trajectory of the nation.

A prominent case study that vividly illustrates the impact of youth unemployment on political stability in Nigeria is the Chibok schoolgirls abduction. In 2014, the abduction of over 200 schoolgirls from Chibok in North East, Nigeria, by the extremist group Boko Haram sent shockwaves across the nation and the world (Ajayi, 2014:366-377). The attackers, many of whom were unemployed youths, exploited their vulnerability and hopelessness to perpetrate a heinous act that undermined the Nigerian government's legitimacy and its ability to ensure the safety of its citizens. This case serves as a stark reminder of the security risks posed by unemployed youth and their potential to destabilise the political landscape (Aliyu, 2016:59-72).

Moreover, in Eastern Nigeria, the historical Biafra secessionist movement has resurfaced in recent years, with youth unemployment playing a significant role in the resurgence of these calls for secession (Oyekanmi, 2017:51-64). The lack of economic opportunities in the region has fueled sentiments of marginalisation and discontent among the youth, making them susceptible to secessionist propaganda. The Biafra agitation poses a notable challenge to political stability in Nigeria and requires careful policy responses that address the economic grievances of the youth while preserving national unity (Ndubuisi, 2019:61-83). Also, the Niger Delta region has been a hotspot of militancy and resource conflict, partly driven by youth unemployment (Ekine, 2013:148-169). The pervasive poverty and lack of economic opportunities in the region have created a fertile ground for discontent and militancy, while the impact of youth unemployment on political stability cannot be over-emphasised. The youth, lacking alternatives, have been drawn into illegal activities such as oil theft and attacks on infrastructure, jeopardising the region's political stability (Omeje, 2006:47-50).

The United Nation Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a comprehensive template for addressing poverty and youth restiveness in Nigeria by emphasising the interconnected nature of socio-economic challenges. Goals such as Goal 1 (No Poverty) and Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) target poverty reduction and job creation, addressing key drivers of youth

restiveness. Additionally, Goal 4 (Quality Education) focuses on providing educational opportunities, contributing to skill development and empowerment, which is crucial for mitigating youth restiveness and fostering sustainable socio-economic development. The UN Sustainable Development Goals serve as a holistic framework for addressing poverty and youth restiveness in Nigeria, emphasising the need for multi-dimensional interventions. This approach aligns with the overarching goal of sustainable development, ensuring that efforts to alleviate poverty are interconnected with strategies that empower the youth and promote long-term socio-economic stability (United Nations, 2015).

Socio-Economic Implications and Future Prospects

The socio-economic implications of current challenges in Nigeria extend beyond immediate concerns, influencing the country's long-term prospects. The persistence of poverty and youth restiveness has implications for human capital development and economic productivity (Ogwumike & Alamu, 2018:25-32). High levels of youth unemployment, a direct consequence of these challenges, limit the nation's potential for harnessing its demographic dividend and realising sustained economic growth. The youth population of Nigeria, a demographic powerhouse, is grappling with a multifaceted challenge that transcends economic hardship and social exclusion. One significant aspect of youth restiveness in the country centers on the allure of gambling and participation in illicit trades. This phenomenon is not only a by-product of underlying socio-economic issues but also a distinct challenge that requires nuanced analysis. Nigerian youths are increasingly drawn into the world of gambling, enticed by the prospects of quick financial gains. The proliferation of betting shops, casinos, and online gambling platforms has made it easier for young individuals to engage in gambling activities. This trend is indicative of both the allure and consequences of gambling. While it offers a temporary escape from economic hardships, it often exacerbates financial vulnerabilities, leading to indebtedness and even criminal behavior (Adelabu, 2013:57-73). Gambling's appeal to youth, primarily driven by a desire to overcome poverty, is a significant facet of youth restiveness in Nigeria.

Beyond gambling, many Nigerian youths find themselves involved in illicit trades, including drug trafficking, cyber-crime, and illegal oil bunkering. These activities, often driven by economic desperation, present complex challenges. Involvement in these trades poses a threat to individual lives and the nation's security and stability. The easy access to cyber tools and the desperation to escape poverty have led many youths to engage in cyber-crime, a global concern that Nigeria has not been immune to (Famakinwa & Famakinwa, 2020:28-40). Additionally, the illegal oil bunkering industry in the Niger Delta region offers enticing financial rewards, drawing young individuals into activities that undermine both economic prosperity and national security. Addressing the involvement of Nigerian youths in illicit trades requires a multi-pronged approach that encompasses economic empowerment, education, and law enforcement strategies.

To mitigate the challenges posed by gambling and participation in illicit trades, Nigerian policymakers must address the root causes. The allure of quick wealth through gambling and the temptations of illicit trades often stem from the lack of economic opportunities, limited access to quality education, and insufficient social support structures for the youth. By investing in job creation, skill development, and mentorship programs, Nigeria can empower its youth to make positive choices and become active contributors to the nation's growth (Ezirim, 2016:1-9).

Moreover, a holistic approach is necessary to tackle the complex issue of illicit trades, requiring both law enforcement efforts and socio-economic initiatives to dissuade youth from these activities. The success of these endeavours is integral to alleviating youth restiveness and fostering a more stable and prosperous Nigeria.

Meanwhile, the benefits of technological advancements, when harnessed inclusively, can significantly contribute to the sustainable development of youth, mitigating poverty and restiveness, not only for economic empowerment but also fostering social cohesion and creating avenues for constructive youth engagement. The transformative potential of technology in providing new avenues for skill acquisition, entrepreneurship, and employment opportunities for the youth (Afolayan et al. 2021:875-894) Therefore, it is imperative for government policy in ensuring that technological advancements are accessible and leveraged effectively as this holds the key to fostering a more resilient and dynamic socio-economic landscape for Nigerian youth. Undoubtedly, strategies for poverty alleviation, youth empowerment, and inclusive economic growth are essential for fostering sustainable development in Nigeria. There is need for targeted interventions that address the root causes of poverty and promote inclusive economic growth, acknowledging the interconnected challenges faced by the youth (Eneanya et al, 2022:45-66). Implementing multifaceted strategies, such as comprehensive skill development programs and entrepreneurship support, is crucial for creating a conducive environment for poverty reduction and empowering the youth to contribute meaningfully to the nation's economy. Youth restiveness in Nigeria is a pressing concern that has ramifications for the country's democratic stability and overall nation-building efforts. The future prospects of Nigeria hinge on the effectiveness of policy interventions in addressing these challenges, and recognising the importance of comprehensive measures that extend beyond traditional economic interventions is essential for addressing the nuanced challenges of poverty and youth restiveness, as it takes into account the diverse and context-specific factors influencing these issues. By embracing a integrated perspective, policymakers can formulate more effective strategies that resonate with the cultural intricacies of the Nigerian society, contributing to sustainable development.

Civil society organisations (CSOs) have emerged as crucial actors in Nigeria's democratic landscape, advocating for transparency, accountability, and the protection of citizens' rights. In the context of mitigating youth restiveness, CSOs play a pivotal role as intermediaries between disenfranchised youth and the government. They provide platforms for constructive dialogue, advocacy, and the channeling of youth concerns into actionable policy recommendations (Omotola, 2011:71-87). The proactive engagement of CSOs helps to bridge the gap between disenchanted youth and government institutions, fostering mutual understanding and trust. They also contribute to mitigating youth restiveness by promoting civic education and engagement by organising workshops, training sessions, and awareness campaigns, They also empower the youth with knowledge of their rights, responsibilities, and the democratic processes. This education instills a sense of civic duty and encourages active participation in peaceful and constructive forms of activism (Amuwo, 2003:283-301). Such initiatives enhance the youth's capacity to engage with the government and other stakeholders, making them more effective advocates for change. Another vital dimension of civil society's role in mitigating youth restiveness is its advocacy for inclusive policies. CSOs actively monitor government policies and programs to ensure they address the underlying issues that contribute to youth restiveness, such as unemployment,

education, and healthcare (Amundsen, 2013:104-113). Through research, policy analysis, and public campaigns, CSOs influence the design and implementation of policies that genuinely cater to the needs of the youth, promoting social justice and reducing the potential for unrest. Olowu (2003:155-175) affirms that:

Civil society also serves as a watchdog, holding the government accountable for its actions and decisions, while their active monitoring of government initiatives and spending ensures that resources are allocated transparently and effectively, reducing the potential for corruption and mismanagement that can exacerbate youth restiveness.

The scrutiny provided by civil society acts as a deterrent to the misuse of power and resources, reinforcing democratic governance and, in turn, promoting political stability. The collaboration between government, civil society, and the private sector plays a pivotal role in implementing effective policies that address poverty and youth restiveness in Nigeria. The importance of a multi-stakeholder approach between these sectors enhances the efficiency and impact of policy initiatives (Iheanachor et al., 2022:102-117). This collaborative synergy is essential for ensuring a holistic and sustainable development trajectory that addresses the complex challenges facing the nation. The significance of adopting a holistic approach that incorporates social and cultural dimensions in policymaking cannot be overemphasised (Adetola et al., 2023:45-68).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the intricate interplay of poverty and youth restiveness within the Nigerian political and economic landscape demands a comprehensive and nuanced approach. The historical legacy, characterised by colonial imprints, military interventions, and economic policy shifts, has left a lasting impact on the challenges faced by the nation. Addressing these issues necessitates not only targeted economic policies but also a re-evaluation of governance structures, political will, and a commitment to inclusivity. Moving forward, it is imperative to heed the lessons learned from failed policies and gaps in governance. Implementing evidence-based strategies, leveraging technological advancements inclusively, and adopting holistic approaches that consider cultural and social dimensions are paramount. The UN Sustainable Development Goals offer a valuable framework, aligning global aspirations with the specific needs of Nigeria. By embracing these principles and fostering collaboration between government, civil society, and the private sector, there is a prospect for sustainable development that uplifts the youth, mitigates poverty, and establishes a resilient socio-economic foundation for Nigeria's future. This paper contributes to academic knowledge by providing a comprehensive analysis of the Nigerian political and economic landscape, unraveling the intricate dynamics of poverty and youth restiveness, and proposing evidence-based recommendations for sustainable development.

Recommendations

In the light of the complex challenges outlined in the preceding analysis, the following five recommendations emerge as crucial pathways for policymakers and stakeholders to address poverty and youth restiveness in Nigeria. Investing in comprehensive education and skill

development initiatives is crucial for empowering the youths and preparing them for the evolving job market. Also enhancing civic education programs to educate citizens, especially the youths, about their rights and responsibilities in a democracy can foster a more politically aware and engaged population. By aligning these programs with Sustainable Development Goals 4 (Quality Education) and 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), Nigeria can foster a skilled workforce, stimulate economic productivity, and reduce youth restiveness.

Addressing the digital division is imperative for creating equal opportunities. Emphasising the importance of digital literacy and providing accessible technology can bridge socio-economic disparities. Nigeria should prioritise policies that promote inclusive governance, transcending ethnic and regional divisions to ensure equal political participation and representation for all. Aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), this recommendation aims to leverage technology to empower the youth and enhance economic inclusivity.

Corruption undermines effective governance and exacerbates poverty. Strengthening anti-corruption measures, aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions), is essential for creating a transparent and accountable political and economic environment. This, in turn, can foster public trust, attract investments, and contribute to sustainable development.

Fostering collaboration between the government, civil society, and the private sector, as emphasised in Sustainable Development Goal 17 (Partnerships for the Goals), is critical for effective policy implementation. By harnessing the strengths of each sector, Nigeria can create a synergistic and adaptive approach to address the multifaceted challenges of poverty and youth restiveness. Also fostering community engagement and participation by encouraging open dialogue among ethnic and identity groups which is crucial for building understanding, trust, and a shared sense of national identity for nation-building and democratic stability. This suggestion is in alignment with Sustainable Development Goals 10 (Reduced Inequalities) and 17 (Partnerships for the Goals), to ensure that policies are contextually relevant and inclusive.

Finally, by emphasising investment in sustainable agriculture and entrepreneurship, this recommendation aligns with Sustainable Development Goals 1 (No Poverty), 2 (Zero Hunger), and 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), aiming to diversify the economy, create employment opportunities, and alleviate poverty in rural and urban areas.

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